

Investigating the Grade 12 Senior High School Learners' Engagement in English Online Classroom during the COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract: This study aimed to identify the level of engagement of Grade 12 senior high school learners in English classroom settings when online learning was adopted. It also intended to analyze how they felt about receiving instructions in an online environment as well as the relationship between the learners' engagement and feelings about attending online English classes. The study primarily employed a quantitative research approach using a modified questionnaire of Handelsman et al.'s (2005) Student Course Engagement Questionnaire (SCEQ). The results showed that learners demonstrated engagement with their online English classes in relation to several constructs of engagement. Specifically, it was evident in the survey responses that the learners showed engagement through classroom participation, engagement through interaction with instructors and peers, engagement through skills practice, engagement through their emotional involvement with the class material, and engagement through their performance in class. These findings indicate that a move toward online classes can be effective as they highlight the potential of online learning in reshaping and optimizing educational experiences, offering opportunities for deeper student involvement and learning outcomes.

Keywords: COVID-19 pandemic, senior high school students, online engagement, online learning, English classes

I. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused disruptions to schools and classes around the world that made school authorities to suddenly shift to synchronous mode in order to accommodate and to continue the formal learning of students. The sudden shift from face to face to online learning has made a serious impact among students adjusting to the new norm of learning. The pandemic might have created difficulties and challenges towards learning among students; however, they need to continue learning and to find ways in coping up to the new situation. Munroe (2021) explains that online education is the most effective alternative for students to continue their learning at home during the time of pandemic. Furthermore, with the pandemic affecting all countries worldwide, e-learning and blended learning is the plan for the new normal education system that would meet the needs of students (Cortez, 2020).

Not known by many, long before the declaration of the world-wide health emergency, several universities in the Philippines are already employing online platforms as mode of teaching; they are the UPOU, De La Salle University, Ateneo De Manila University, University of Santo Tomas, and the Asian Institute of Management. In a newspaper interview in 2020 with Prof. Centeno (UPLB), he stated that educational technologies are proven to be efficient and even encourage students to be more active in facilitating their own learning. However, an array of challenges facing the sudden shift from the traditional method in teaching to the online modality platform includes the readiness of both teachers and students.

According to Karagüven (2010) as cited by Javaeed et al (2019) academically motivated students are capable of learning, active in participating in educational activities, and have a better improvement academically. In addition, Dramanu and Mohammed's (2017) study indicated that there is a positive correlation between students' academic motivation and academic performance. A positive and high engagement in classes is invested by these academically motivated students to face scholastic challenges. Student engagement with emphasis on cognitive engagement, academic self-efficacy and motivation according to Dogan (2017) affect academic performance. In line with Handelsman et al. definition of engagement and concentrating on the microlevel of 'what happens in and immediately surrounding class' (Al-Sheikh, 2020).

Through a variety of pathways, student engagement, learner interaction, and instructor presence have accounted for significant differences in student satisfaction and perceived learning in online learning settings (Gray & Diloreto, 2016). A research entitled Grade 12 Students' Perceptions on Distance Learning in General Chemistry was conducted. The purpose of this study, which is based on evidence from the Philippines, is to determine students' perceptions of the use of synchronous and asynchronous distant learning resources at the Grade 12 level. It emphasizes students' preferences for synchronous and asynchronous modes of instruction delivery. The 317 participants were chosen at random from a group of Grade 12 students enrolled in the Special Health Sciences STEM track at a private medical institution in Cavite City's urban area. These Grade 12 students have had extensive experience in both synchronous and asynchronous online programs.

According to students' replies, both methods have their own set of benefits and drawbacks. However, as a supplement to traditional classes during pandemics and community lockdowns, these alternative modalities are unquestionably valuable and efficient instruments. With the integration of additional interactive technology-based apps, it improved pedagogical instructions and students' conceptual understanding, making virtual learning more meaningful and worthwhile. Students' learning experiences were boosted by the use of technology, which supplied a vast network of knowledge. The facilitator function of the online teacher is critical in the introduction of alternate learning modalities. They have the ability to make the virtual learning environment accommodating and comfortable, resulting in a favorable atmosphere.

The framework of Garrison (2000)'s Community of Inquiry (COI) serves as the foundation for this research. The process model not only highlights the important characteristics that make up an ideal and worthwhile learning environment, but it also gives a sense of how online communities of inquiry work. The Community of Inquiry (CoI) model emphasizes three core elements or "presences" of an online educational experience: (1) participants' ability to communicate and develop interpersonal relationships (social presence), (2) learners' engagement with content and critical construction of meaning (cognitive presence), and (3) the design, facilitation, and direction of social and cognitive activities (teaching presence). As a result, CoI, combined with features of good online teaching methods, gives a heuristic approach to creating an online learning environment in General Chemistry.

The majority of students respond well to the use of interactive applications and games like Kahoot and Quizizz to administer exit or formative assessments. With the synthesis of solutions and final replies, they actively connect with their classmates, recollect crucial topics, and thoroughly examine their understanding. Students remark that they pay more attention and participate more actively in class. Presentation, explanation, and discussion of possible responses to the prompt demonstrate active engagement. During synchronous classes, students confidently communicate their ideas, thoughts, and opinions.

Feelings play a significant role in students' psychological well-being, which has a direct impact on their academic progress (Health, 2016; Moeller et al., 2020; Phan et al., 2019). Positive emotions (such as enjoyment and interest) were discovered to be linked to students' attention, focus, engagement, and persistence in learning activities, all of which were found to be positively correlated with academic accomplishment (Eccles, 2005; Moeller et al., 2020; Schiefele, 1996). Negative emotions such as boredom, exhaustion, and anxiety, on the other hand, have been shown to deplete cognitive resources, significantly impacting school performance and academic attainment (Madigan and Curran, 2020; Moeller et al., 2020; Samuel and Burger, 2019). The COVID-19 pandemic has put a huge emotional strain on students of all ages and has put their mental health in jeopardy (Gavin et al., 2020; Grubic et al., 2020; Pfefferbaum and North, 2020). As a result of learners displaying signs of worry and tension, educational institutions around the world are invariably confronted with unforeseen obstacles. A survey of high school students found that stress (29 percent), anxiety (12 percent), and depression (5%) were the most common responses (Moeller et al., 2020).

The results of a weekly assessment of the students' feelings throughout the duration of 8 weeks from the start of the quarantine in Mexico are presented in this study. The online survey was sent to high school students at Tecnológico de Monterrey's 36 campuses, which had a total of 13,000 students. An open-ended poll allowed them to identify a wide range of emotions felt by the students, from which they chose five as the most prominent negative emotions: anxiety, despair, exhaustion, stress, and overload. Overall, 14% of individuals who reported these sensations and, in particular, those who found themselves worried and/or sad, acknowledged the need for professional aid in regulating their emotions. Students of all ages and academic levels have reported poor energy levels and found the lockout circumstances to be uncomfortable or extremely unpleasant. While high school students displayed "fluctuating emotions over the course of an eight-week analysis," undergraduate students' energy levels and emotional valence of feelings continuously decreased.

The purpose of the study on the Modular Distance Learning Implementation in Philippine Public Secondary Schools is to learn about the obstacles that teachers, parents, and students face. It also seeks to determine the strategies, interventions, or solutions for all people involved in the new learning modality adjustment. Modules encourage independent study, and one of the advantages of employing this type of instruction is that students develop superior self-study or learning skills. Students get more engaged in learning the concepts offered in the module as they gain a sense of responsibility for completing the exercises. They are learning how to learn and are becoming more self-assured (Nardo, M.T.B, 2017).

Other benefits of modular instruction include better adaptability of instructional materials, more choice and self-pacing for students, and more diversity and flexibility for teachers and staff. On the other side, students will need more self-discipline and motivation, as well as more preparation time and a lack of clear benefits for teachers and staff, as well as more administrative resources to track students and administer various modules.

This research employs a survey design to identify the issues associated with the use of Modular Distance Learning Modality (MDLM), as well as a descriptive approach to determine the various solutions to these challenges. A survey was used to obtain the thoughts and recommendations of students, parents, and instructors, notably using questionnaires with open-ended questions. The study was done at Balbalayang National High School in a rural area of San Gabriel, La Union, and Baguio City National High School in an urban area of Baguio City, Benguet. Purposive and quota sampling were used to choose fifteen (15) students, twelve (12) parents, and ten (10) school officials as key informants in each of the selected schools. The dissemination of questionnaires and data retrieval were done through email, Google forms, and social media. The researchers' research advisor approved the

localization of the questions used in the questionnaires. The data was interpreted and coded using Deductive Thematic Analysis.

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As a result of the findings, the majority of students are struggling with this new learning method. Ninety percent of the participants struggled to complete their programs. Half of the participants don't have enough time to complete all of the courses in a week. They frequently receive at least 8 modules in all areas, with 3-5 activities in each module. According to the students, Mathematics is the most challenging subject, followed by History, Entrepreneurship, and Applied Economics. Many students report that most of the exercises in mathematics are difficult to solve and that no detailed explanation is provided. Problem solving entails not only calculation but also understanding and analysis of the problem. It is critical that students comprehend the problems (Salma & Rodrigues, 2012). Some learners mentioned that history involves lengthy readings and that many of the students don't comprehend some of the terms. The questions are also difficult, and there aren't many examples. Lessons are difficult for students to comprehend, and history books are extensive (Tok, B. R 2016).

Cortez's research, C. P. (2020) The New Normal of Mathematics Education: Blended, Distance, Electronic, and Virtual Learning Due to CoViD-19, A Senior High School Student's Perception examines senior high school students' perceptions of blended, distant, electronic, and virtual learning as a new means of delivering courses for the school year 2020-2021. The participants in this study were 342 senior high school students from STI College Global City from various strands. To comply with the government's existing lockdown policies, data is shared and gathered using a self-administered survey questionnaire delivered via Google Form. Despite the fact that their estimated mathematical capability is drastically different, the results suggest that the subjects' assessment of the efficiency of online learning and their

capacity to attend e-learning sessions is independent of their lifestyle and available e-learning equipment.

Students can access learning materials such as video tutorials, PowerPoint presentations, and handouts through online classrooms. Educators must be trained to be good designers, content experts, and proficient in the use of hardware and software technologies in order to create effective e-learning materials (Hasmawati Hassan et al., 2012). According to the study's findings, respondents agree that they can learn mathematics at home using electronic materials on average, despite the fact that 90% of them still require the teacher's approval of the lesson. Students' mathematical abilities are said to be classified into strands. With a mean of 6.22 out of 10 and a standard deviation of 1.53, analysis of variance reveals that students in different strands had considerably diverse perceptions of their mathematical abilities.

Despite students' differences in mathematical ability and regardless of their own electronic gadgets, quality of internet connection, and means to connect to the internet, the majority of students believe they are capable of attending online or distance learning and see no difference between attending or being in an actual or physical classroom setting.

Although 76 percent of students think that watching video tutorials helps them learn more, it is notable that 90 percent of students still require validation from their math lecturers when learning mathematics. On average, students "agreed" that video lessons help them learn more, but that they still require their teacher's approval.

This demonstrates that, despite the fact that most people agree that video tutorials may really help students learn arithmetic; validation from teachers is still an important tool for learners to establish confidence in what they learned from a video tutorial.

Online Engagement Framework for higher education (Redmond et al, 2018)

Student engagement is understood to be an important benchmark and indicator of the quality of the student experience for higher education; yet the term engagement continues to be elusive to define and it is interpreted in different ways in the literature. Student engagement is widely recognized as a key benchmark and indicator of the quality of the student experience in higher education; nonetheless, the phrase remains challenging to define, and it is interpreted in various ways in the literature (Redmond et al, 2018).

Although the term "engagement" is often used, it appears to have a variety of definitions and interpretations. (Dixson, 2015; Lawson & Lawson, 2013; Taylor & Parsons, 2011). This is especially true in colleges, where student engagement has risen to new heights. According to Gibbs (2014), the term "now refers to so many various topics which are difficult to make sense of what people are actually talking about." Gibbs (2014), "one of the most

ubiquitous buzzwords.” While student engagement, according to Krause (2005), is a catch-all term that is most typically used to represent a collection of behaviors that involve student learning.

Redmond et al, (2018) According to the authors, the online engagement framework provided here is a multifaceted construct with interconnected factors that influence student participation in online settings. Academics can use the framework to reflect on learner engagement in their online courses, and even the implications for personal classroom instruction, course design, and, ideally, program design.

Online Engagement Element	Indicators (illustrative only)
Social engagement	Building community Creating a sense of belonging Developing relationships Establishing trust
Cognitive engagement	Thinking critically Activating metacognition Integrating ideas Justifying decisions Developing deep discipline understandings Distributing expertise
Behavioral engagement	Developing academic skills Identifying opportunities and challenges Developing multidisciplinary skills Developing agency Upholding online learning norms Supporting and encouraging peers
Collaborative engagement	Learning with peers Relating to faculty members Connecting to institutional opportunities Developing professional networks
Emotional engagement	Managing expectations Articulating assumptions Recognising motivations Committing to learning

The elements and metrics for each element are summarized in the online engagement framework for higher education provided above. The framework evolved from a social constructionist approach to higher education, in which asynchronous and synchronous group conversations are used to facilitate individual and group learning. It isn't hierarchical or linear in structure, and each aspect is not meant to be studied separately. Rather, the framework serves as a tool for deciphering the fluid nature of online engagement. In relevance, the framework was utilized in the present study as a guide map to explore the skills, emotional, participation/interaction, and performance engagements of the sample population.

The following questions are addressed in this study:

1. What is the level of engagement in English classes among Grade 12 senior high school learners when online learning is adopted?
2. How do Grade 12 senior high school learners feel towards receiving instruction in English classes in an online environment?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the learners' engagement and feelings about their experience of attending online English classes?

II. Methodology

A. Research Design

The study employed a quantitative research approach because it offers a more comprehensive understanding of behavior as well as abundant data about real life people and situations (De Vaus, 2014). It is also defined as a systematic investigation of a phenomenon using a collection of numerical data and the application of statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques (Slevitch, 2011). The quantitative data was gathered through random sampling which entails sending a questionnaire to the target sample and allowing each member to have an opportunity to participate. For the quantitative data, Handelsman et al.'s Student Course Engagement Questionnaire (SCEQ) (2005) was adapted and modified. The researchers reconstructed every item in the questionnaire by using the first person personal pronoun "I" and by changing the tense into present simple forms instead of gerund or non-finite phrases. One item was also modified from 'Going to the professor during office hours to review assignments or tests or to ask questions' to 'I send a message to my English teacher during his/her free time to review assignments or tests, or to ask questions.' because the latter would be more appropriate and relevant to the online class setup due to the COVID-19 outbreak. Before distributing the questionnaire, the researchers evaluated it with teachers and other colleagues to see if there were any ambiguous items.

A pilot research was conducted to test the reliability of the questionnaire. Fraser et al. (2018) believes that a pilot study is highly important to be carried out to see if using a survey questionnaire and the recruitment and data collection techniques are feasible. Regarding the survey sample's responses to the tool, 20 respondents were involved in the pilot study. In addition, it is imperative to note that they had similar characteristics to those of the actual study and were not included in the actual research sample.

An internal consistency test was undertaken to test the reliability of the questionnaire using SPSS software for the entire scale, except for the demographic component. Cronbach's alpha was determined to be 0.932 (see Appendix C, Table A1), which is within the acceptable range (Taber, 2017). All elements are related to their appropriate dimension, as evidenced by the data tabulated (Appendix C Table A2), with a level of significance of 0.01. The validity of the instrument's internal consistency is demonstrated by this finding. It also shows that the items had a statistically significant relationship with the dimension they belonged.

After piloting the study, the survey questionnaire was sent out particularly to the participants' facebook messenger together with a letter of consent to start collecting data. The questionnaire for the main data gathering was generated electronically using Google Forms due to the limits set by the local government. It is also worth noting that the researcher is the economics teacher of some participants which could help reduce the participant expectancy as a threat to validity (Turner, 2014) since they only evaluated their online English classes. The online classes that the participants assessed were the ones that they took since the system shifted to online instructions which included Reading and Writing, Oral Communication, Philippine Literature, and English for Academic and Professional Purposes.

Finally, the descriptive data was derived by coding and analyzing the data using SPSS version 26, R Statistics and Microsoft Office Excel. Since the samples are not normally distributed (see Appendix D), Kruskal-Wallis was then conducted to explore the statistical significance of the learning engagement; and Mann-Whitney U to determine the significant relationship between the learners' feelings about their online experience in English classes and each level of engagements. To check the significant association between quantitative variables, Spearman correlation was utilized with a p-value of <0.05 being considered statistically significant. The study variables consisted of engagement (an independent variable) and the learners' feelings about their experience (the dependent variable).

Hence, this study was conducted to investigate the impact of COVID-19 on learning particularly to the senior high school students in Parañaque City, Philippines. Questionnaires were the primary instrument used for the purpose of this study, since such a design would allow the researchers to collect the most complete and accurate data in a logical flow (Abawi.2017). It would also enable a better understanding of the use of a special teaching and learning platform provided by Zoom Video Communications most commonly known as Zoom.

The study adopted and modified Handelsman et al.'s Student Course Engagement Questionnaire (SCEQ) which was initially designed to measure engagement across certain college courses. This scale was included in the present study to measure engagement with senior high school English online courses (see Appendix B). Al-Sheikh (2020) added that Handelsman et al. constructed the measure mainly for use at micro-level, concerning what happens in and immediately surrounding a class. They stated that they were pursuing engagement from this angle because they thought it was the level over which the practitioner had the most control. Thus, it was the point where the most alterations could be done. According to Ab Rahman et al. (2019), no other scale evaluates students' participation in a single course rather than an entire program, as the National Survey of Student Engagement (NSSE) does. The SCEQ utilized and validated in a number of different studies worldwide (Jezegou, 2013).

Handelsman et al. divided engagement into four different factors from their 23-item measure. In their investigation, the measure had a coefficient alpha of 0.76 to 0.82, indicating strong internal consistency. The first factor was termed "skills engagement" since it shows student engagement through skill practice. The second factor was called 'Emotional engagement,' which is associated with learners' engagement characterized by their emotional involvement with the class material. The third factor, 'participation/interaction engagement,' measures learners' involvement in the classroom as well as through interactions with instructors and peers. Finally, the fourth factor, referred to as "Performance engagement," which relates student engagement to classroom performance.

The study properly addressed some ethical considerations, such as obtaining approval from the participants before the administration of the questionnaire. The principal's approval was also sought. It was stressed that all data would be kept private and only used for the purposes of this study. The findings of this case study were used to provide recommendations for a contemporary EFL online educational program. The study focused entirely on gauging EFL learners' involvement in English classes, with no consideration for other courses.

B. Study Population

Grade 12 senior high school learners in a private high school in the city of Parañaque were asked to participate in the study which was conducted in the first week of September. As previously stated, an electronic questionnaire was sent to the participants in a private co-educational institution in Parañaque City, and each participant was asked to sign the consent (see Appendix A) which was sent separately prior to the main questionnaire. In line with the characteristics presented in Table 1 below, 71 senior high school students agreed to participate in the study, comprising 29% of the overall population of the Grade 12 study community.

Table 1. Characteristics of the participants (n = 71).

	Categories	N	%
Strand	ABM	44	62%
	GAS	13	18.3%
	STEM	14	19.7%
Age	16 years	2	2.8%
	17 years	44	62%
	18 years	25	35.2%
City	Parañaque	66	93%
	Others	5	7%
Gender	Male	32	45.1%
	Female	39	54.9%
	Total	71	100%

III. Results

To answer the initial inquiry of the research study, ‘What is the level of engagement in English classes among Grade 12 senior high school learners when online learning is adopted?’; the researchers found that the engagement in English classes among Grade 12 senior high school learners when online learning was adopted, was generally at a moderately high level of ‘Characteristic of me’ (mean = 3.90, SD = 0.520). Here, ‘Performance engagement’ was ranked first (mean = 4.23, SD = 0.409), indicated as ‘Characteristic of me’; ‘Skills engagement’ was ranked second (mean = 4.08, SD = 0.426), indicated as ‘Characteristic of me’; ‘Emotional engagement’ was ranked third (mean = 3.84, SD = 0.603), indicated as ‘Characteristic of me’, and ‘Participation/interaction engagement’ was ranked fourth (mean = 3.46, SD = 0.640), indicated as ‘Moderately characteristic of me’.

A. Skills Engagement

When online learning was adopted, skills engagement in English classes among Grade 12 senior high school learners was generally at the level: ‘Characteristic of me,’ as shown in Table 2.(mean = 4.09, SD = 0.564). This potentially indicates that the students had skills engagement in English subjects they were taking in an online setting.

Table 2. Descriptive data for the students' skills engagement

N o.	Item	Me an	SD	Arrange ment	Level of Engagement
1	I make sure to study on a regular basis for my English online classes.	3.8 3	0.7 17	8	Characteristic of me
2	I put so much effort into my English online classes.	3.9 3	0.8 51	6	Characteristic of me
3	I do all the homework for my English online classes.	4.6 1	0.6 65	2	Very characteristic of me
4	I stay up on the readings for my English online classes.	3.6 2	0.8 68	9	Characteristic of me
5	I look over my notes between classes to make sure I understand the lessons for my English online classes.	3.9 4	0.8 26	5	Characteristic of me
6	I am organized for my English online classes.	3.9 0	0.7 40	7	Characteristic of me
7	I take good notes for my English online classes.	3.9 9	0.9 33	4	Characteristic of me
8	I listen carefully in my English online classes.	4.2 8	0.6 37	3	Characteristic of me
9	I attend my English online classes every day.	4.6 2	0.5 94	1	Very characteristic of me
<i>Skills Engagement</i>		4.0 8	0.4 26	-	Characteristic of me

'Attending online English classes every day' was indicated as 'Very characteristic of me' and ranked first (mean = 4.62, SD = 0.594); 'Doing all homework problems' was likewise indicated as 'Characteristic of me' and ranked second (mean = 4.61, SD = 0.665), while 'Listening carefully in English online classes' was ranked third (mean = 4.28, SD = 0.637), indicated as 'Characteristic of me'. The results indicate that the learners had skills engagement (mean = 4.08, SD = 0.426).

B. Emotional Engagement

When online learning was implemented, emotional engagement in English classes among Grade 12 senior high school learners was generally at the level: 'Characteristic of me,' as shown in Table 3 (mean = 3.84, SD = 0.603). Based on the results, since they responded positively to these elements on the scale, the learners were emotionally engaged in the classroom setting, and the scale reflected their emotional engagement as emotional

involvement with the class material. For example, ‘Really desiring to learn the online English lessons/materials’ was ranked first (mean = 4.01, SD = 0.886), indicated as ‘Characteristic of me’. Meanwhile, ‘Finding ways to make English online lessons relevant to their lives’ and ‘Applying the English online lessons/materials to their lives’ were both ranked second with (mean = 3.97, SD = 0.792) and (mean = 3.97, SD = 0.861) respectively, with a level of engagement indicated as ‘Characteristic of me’, and ‘Finding ways to make English online classes interesting to them’ was ranked third (mean = 3.92, SD = 0.788) as ‘Characteristic of me’.

Table 3. Descriptive data for the students’ emotional engagement.

N o.	Item	Me an	SD	Arrange ment	Level Engagement	of
1	I find ways to make the English online lessons relevant to my life.	3.97	0.792	2	Characteristic of me	of
2	I apply the English online course materials/lessons to my life.	3.97	0.861	2	Characteristic of me	of
3	I find ways to make the English online classes interesting to me.	3.92	0.788	3	Characteristic of me	of
4	I think about the English online courses/subjects between class meetings.	3.31	0.785	4	Moderately characteristic of me	of
5	I really desire to learn my online English lessons/materials.	4.01	0.886	1	Characteristic of me	of
<i>Emotional Engagement</i>		3.84	0.603	-	Characteristic of me	of

C. Participation/Interaction Engagement

In Table 4, the participation/interaction engagement in English classes among Grade 12 senior high school learners, when online learning was implemented, was generally at the level: ‘Moderately characteristic of me’ (mean = 3.46, SD = 0.640). For instance, the following points elicited responses from the students: ‘Helping fellow classmates in English’ was ranked first (mean = 3.72, SD = 0.988), with a level of engagement defined as ‘Characteristic of me’; ‘Having fun in English online classes’ was ranked second (mean = 3.66, SD = 0.810), with a level of engagement ranked as ‘Characteristic of me’, and ‘Participating actively in small group discussions for their English online classes’ was ranked third (mean = 3.54, SD = 1.026), with a level of engagement indicated as ‘Characteristic of me’. The results reveal that the learners had moderate participation/interaction engagement (mean = 3.46, SD = 0.640).

Table 4. Descriptive data for the students' participation/interaction engagement

No.	Item	Mean	SD	Arrange ment	Level Engagement
1	I raise my hand in my English online classes.	3.24	1.021	5	Moderately characteristic of me
2	I ask questions when I don't understand my English teacher/instructor during the online class.	3.46	1.040	4	Moderately characteristic of me
3	I have fun in my English online classes.	3.66	0.810	2	Characteristic of me
4	I participate actively in small group discussions for my English online classes.	3.54	1.026	3	Characteristic of me
5	I send a message to my English teacher during his/her free time to review assignments or tests, or to ask questions.	3.17	1.095	6	Moderately characteristic of me
6	I help my fellow classmates in English.	3.72	0.988	1	Characteristic of me
<i>Participation/Interaction Engagement</i>		3.46	0.640	-	Moderately characteristic of me

D. Performance Engagement

It can be seen in Table 5 that the performance engagement in English classes among Grade 12 senior high school learners, when online learning was adopted, was generally at the level: 'Characteristic of me' (mean = 4.23, SD = 0.409). One of the primary goals of any educational program should be to instill and foster a sense of aspiration to achieve completion and better proficiency. Here, the learners expressed the most agreement with the following statements: 'Being confident that they can learn or do well in English online classes/subjects' was ranked first (mean = 4.54, SD = 0.556), with a level of engagement indicated as 'Very characteristic of me'; 'Doing well in English tests' was ranked second (mean = 4.14, SD = 0.515), with a level of engagement indicated as 'Characteristic of me', and 'Getting good grades in English subjects' was ranked third (mean = 4.00, SD = 0.609), with a level of engagement indicated as 'Characteristic of me'. The results indicate that the learners had a performance engagement (mean = 4.23, SD = 0.409).

Table 5. Descriptive data for the students' performance engagement

N	Item	Mean	SD	Arrange ment	Level of Engagement
1	I get good grades in my English subjects.	4.00	0.609	3	Characteristic of me
2	I do well in English tests.	4.14	0.515	2	Characteristic of me
3	I am confident that I can learn and do well in English online classes/subjects.	4.54	0.556	1	Very characteristic of me
<i>Performance Engagement</i>		4.23	0.409	-	Characteristic of me

Furthermore, a test of statistical correlation was also conducted (see Appendix E), where it can be observed that there is a significant relationship between all engagement factors similar to the original study, except for the relationship between emotional and performance engagement which may be potentially inconclusive due to the smaller number of participants ($n=71$) in contrast to the original study ($n=379$).

To answer the second question, 'How do Grade 12 senior high school learners feel towards receiving instruction in English classes in an online environment?' It was found that 49.3% of the students were 'Satisfied' with their experience of attending English classes, 45.1% were 'Neutral', and just 5.6% were 'Very satisfied' (see Table 6). Over half of the students expressed satisfaction with their online learning experience, indicating that they were engaged in the class. While less than half of the respondents were somewhat satisfied or unsatisfied with their experience. These data were then subjected to further analysis.

Table 6. Descriptive data for students' feelings about their online learning experience.

Variable	Categories	N	%
How do you feel about attending English classes virtually?	Very Satisfied	4	5.6
	Satisfied	35	49.3
	Neutral	32	45.1
	Unsatisfied	0	0
	Very Unsatisfied	0	0

On conducting a Kruskal-Wallis test, overall, it may be seen from Table 7A that there was a significant difference among learners' engagements (Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared: 59.422, $P < 0.01$). A significant relationship was also found between learners' engagement

and their feelings about their English online learning experience as shown in Table 7B, except the relationship between the participation/interaction engagement and the learners' feelings (Mann-Whitney U: 2237.50; $P > 0.05$) which was deemed as not statistically significant which means that the strength of relationship in the sample would more unlikely be observed in the population that the study purports to represent.

Table 7A. A test of significant difference among types of learners' engagement.

Kruskal Wallis chi-squared	59.422
P-value	< .001**

Table 7B. Relationship between the learners' engagement and feelings about their experience of attending online English classes

Variables		N	Mann-Whitney U	p- Value*
Skill engagement	Neutral	32	1297.50	< .001**
	Satisfied	35		
	Very Satisfied	4		
Emotional Engagement	Neutral	32	1941.00	0.016**
	Satisfied	35		
	Very Satisfied	4		
Participation/Interaction Engagement	Neutral	32	2237.50	0.239
	Satisfied	35		
	Very Satisfied	4		
Performance Engagement	Neutral	32	989.50	< .001**
	Satisfied	35		
	Very Satisfied	4		

An open-ended question was also added to the questionnaire, with the purpose to obtain more insight from the students by allowing them to explain why they were satisfied or unsatisfied with their online learning experience. The themes in the responses were organized using content analysis. The frequency of specific topics in the texts was recognized after reviewing the valid responses (see Tables 8 and 9).

Table 8. The responses given by the learners for being neutral with their experience of learning English in an online learning environment.

Reasons for Not Being Neutral with the Online Environment	No. of Responses	%	Examples
Poor internet connection	7	41.2%	"Sometimes we have bad internet connection"
Problems in understanding	3	17.6%	"It is hard to understand the discussions"
Difficulties in concentration	3	17.6%	"I cannot concentrate"
Lack of real interaction	2	11.8%	"I badly miss face to face interaction"
Accepting the online environment	2	11.8%	" <i>Hindi ko feel ang online class</i> "
Total	17	100%	

Table 9. Responses given for being satisfied with the experience of learning English in an online environment.

Reasons for Being Satisfied with the Online Environment	No. of Responses	%	Examples
To limit the spread of the virus	8	28.6%	"Satisfied with the experience because it is safer to stay home"
Helping us to concentrate more	5	18.0%	"It gives me more time to read and to study"
Easier to understand	4	14.2%	"I understand the lessons well"
Independency in learning	4	14.2%	"More independent in learning"
Efficacy of the strategies used	3	10.7%	"Nice strategies and exciting games and drills"
Saving time and effort	2	7.1%	" <i>Nakakasave ako ng oras para sa ibang bagay</i> "
New experience	1	3.6%	"Exciting. A good way to learn"
Reducing negative feelings (anxiety and stress)	1	3.6%	"It gives me a chance to participate. I feel less shy."
Total	28	100%	

As described by Handelsman et al. (2005), the responses to this question show the various levels of student engagement in a classroom setting. It is clear from these findings that the students were engaged in their online English sessions. They described their encounter as satisfying due to their engagement.

IV. Discussion & Conclusion

Based on the results presented in this paper, the sampled learners showed engagement with their online English classes in relation to several constructs of engagement with their course. Specifically, it was evident in the survey responses that the learners showed engagement through classroom participation, engagement through interaction with instructors and peers, engagement through skills practice, engagement through their emotional involvement with the class material, and engagement through their performance in class. These findings indicate that a move toward online classes can be effective. They support that the different types of engagement considered in this study may be enhanced in various ways as a result of studying online, in comparison with traditional teaching. The findings of the study help strengthen the generalizability of the findings found in the original study, particularly the high significance of the learners' engagement and the order of engagements in terms of the level of significance (1) performance engagement, (2) skills engagement, (3) emotional engagement, and (4) participation/interaction engagement.

In conclusion, a variety of needs have necessitated a worldwide educational reform. To engage learners in the new medium, however, it is necessary to first understand what they are currently familiar with (Nasir et al., 2020). By changing familiarity into something fresh

and helpful, this will help to make the classroom a more meaningful experience (Pennington et al., 2019). Given the numerous ways in which remote learning facilitates interaction, it is possible to construct a dynamic environment that changes in response to students' individual differences, as seen by teachers' and learners' collaborative efforts (Alfifi, 2020). We may argue that COVID-19's main benefit is to highlight the utility and potential of this innovative way of teaching and learning, as well as its implementation in the current educational system around the world. Traditional learning, in any event, has already been damaged by the rapid global growth of technology, which has had a particular impact in the Philippines. Because of the nature of the emergency situations in which we live, online and/or distance learning has become an immediate necessity for high school education institutions (Thomas, 2017). We believe that learning will never be the same again, with learning becoming more dynamic, entertaining, and engaging than ever before. As a result, educators must embrace these new shifts with open arms and minds.

Consequently, the students grappled with the rapid change in curriculum delivery, which necessitated a concurrent adjustment in learning approaches. To keep students engaged in an online curriculum, educators must realize their needs, motivations, and previous experiences (Chen et al., 2019). In addition, the teacher's role must shift from authoritative to collaborative and engaging. Teachers in a collaborative classroom work in an interactive atmosphere that emphasizes aural and visual stimulation. The teacher's responsibility here is not just to present the subject; it also includes introducing learners to innovative new learning approaches. As a result, students become producers, designers, and authors, crafting their own experiences and actively contributing to a classroom's learning environment (Mahboob, 2014). Students must be guided in establishing self-regulated learning skills such as time management, metacognition, critical thinking, and effort regulation in order to attain academic achievement (Broadbent, 2015). It is also important to note that the pandemic had caused learners psychological stress, making it challenging for them to concentrate on their studies. Anxiety, burnout, loneliness, homesickness, despair, and hopelessness were among the emotions they experienced. More research is needed to elucidate these characteristics and examine learners' engagement in a broader context (Cao et al., 2020).

The following procedure is suggested based on current research: 1. A larger sample is encouraged to determine the statistical significance of participation and interaction engagement of the learners as well as to be more conclusive with the findings. 2. The study can also be applied to all senior high school learners across strands including Grade 11 students. Due to limited accessibility and the short time period available to the researchers for data collection, this study's sample was solely for Grade 12 students. 3. Follow-up interviews with participants to gain a better understanding of their feelings: doing additional in-depth interviews using semi-structured or open interviews could aid in gaining a better grasp of the impact and reception of online education.

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Appendix A

Consent Form

You are kindly invited to take part in a brief survey, which will consist of this online questionnaire. It has about 23 items and should take no more than 10 minutes to finish. The purpose of the survey is to find out how you feel about online learning and how engaged you are in online English classes. You have the option to leave the survey at any time. The information you provide will be used solely for the purpose of this study and will have no bearing on your grades. Every attempt will be taken to keep the information obtained private. Your willingness to take part in this survey will be greatly appreciated, and you will be making a significant addition to my research. Thanks a lot.

Yours sincerely,

For further details, please feel free to contact the researchers, at any time on:

Email: menard_irac@dlsu.edu.ph

Statement of consent: I hereby agree to take part in this survey. I understand that the data will be protected and sign accordingly,

Participant's signature

Agree

Do not agree

Appendix B

Questionnaire

Part 1:

1. Strandi: ABM GAS STEM

2. Age:

3. City: Parañaque City Others: _____

4. Gender: Female Male

5. How do you feel about attending English language classes through the online environment? Very Satisfied Satisfied Neutral Unsatisfied Very Unsatisfied

Kindly, add your reasons

Part 2:

A. To what extent do the following statements describe your behavior and feelings while studying online for your English online classes? On the scale provided, please select the statement that best describes your feelings and behavior:

5 = Very characteristic of me

4 = Characteristic of me

3 = Moderately characteristic of me

2 = Not really characteristic of me

1 = Not at all characteristic of me

1. I make sure to study on a regular basis for my English online classes.
2. I put so much effort into my English online classes.
3. I do all the homework for my English online classes.
4. I stay up on the readings for my English online classes.
5. I look over my notes between classes to make sure I understand the lessons for my English online classes.
6. I am organized for my English online classes.
7. I take good notes for my English online classes.

8. I listen carefully in my English online classes.
9. I attend my English online classes every day.
10. I find ways to make the English online lessons relevant to my life.
11. I apply the English online course materials/lessons to my life.
12. I find ways to make the English online classes interesting to me.
13. I think about the English online courses/subjects between class meetings.
14. I really desire to learn my online English lessons/materials.
15. I raise my hand in my English online classes.
16. I ask questions when I don't understand my English teacher/instructor during the online class.
17. I have fun in my English online classes.
18. I participate actively in small group discussions for my English online classes.
19. I send a message to my English teacher during his/her free time to review assignments or tests, or to ask questions.
20. I help my fellow classmates in English.
21. I get good grades in my English subjects.
22. I do well in English tests.
23. I am confident that I can learn and do well in English online classes/subjects.

Appendix C

Table A1. Cronbach's alpha.

Factors	No. of Item	Cronbach's alpha
Skill engagement	9	0.861
Emotional engagement	5	0.773
Participation/interaction engagement	6	0.733
Performance engagement	3	0.856
Overall	23	0.932

Table A2. Pearson's correlation coefficient between the item and the factor to which it belongs.

Skill Engagement		Emotional Engagement		Participation/Interaction Engagement		Performance Engagement	
No.	R	No.	R	No.	R	No.	R
All items	0.7205**	All items	0.7836**	All items	0.711**	All items	0.5584**
1	0.7223**	10	0.7383**	15	0.6479**	21	0.3069**
2	0.6668**	11	0.7265**	16	0.6624**	22	0.4023**
3	0.6826**	12	0.7201**	17	0.6938**	23	0.6193**
4	0.7055**	13	0.7887**	18	0.6423**	4	0.7055**
5	0.6786**	14	0.7367**	19	0.6897**	5	0.6786**
6	0.7088**			20	0.6905**	6	0.7088**
7	0.6725**					7	0.6725**

8	0.6921**	8	0.6921**
9	0.7244**	9	0.7244**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Appendix D

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk	Statistic	df	Sig.
	Statistic	df	Sig.				
LF	0.295	71	0.000	0.739	71	0.000	
SE	0.090	71	.200*	0.981	71	0.376	
EE	0.107	71	0.043	0.973	71	0.121	
PIE	0.070	71	.200*	0.989	71	0.822	
PE	0.171	71	0.000	0.925	71	0.000	

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk	Statistic	df	Sig.
	Statistic	df	Sig.				
Log_LF	0.312	71	0.000	0.735	71	0.000	

Log_S E	0.109	71	0.03 6	0.971	7 1	0.10 6
Log_E E	0.115	71	0.02 0	0.955	7 1	0.01 2
Log_P IE	0.105	71	0.05 1	0.971	7 1	0.10 1
Log_P E	0.178	71	0.00 0	0.919	7 1	0.00 0

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Appendix E

Factors	Mea n	SD	Skills Engagem ent	Emotiona l Engagem ent	Participation/Inte raction Engagement	Performa nce Engagem ent
Skills Engagement	4.08	0.42 6	-	0.658**	0.614**	0.328**
Emotional Engagement	3.84	0.60 3	0.658**	-	0.557**	0.223
Participation/Inte raction Engagement	3.46	0.64	0.614**	0.557**	-	0.285**
Performance Engagement	4.23	0.40 9	0.328**	0.223	0.285**	-

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).